

An Optimization Model of CMMI-Based Software Project Risk Response Planning

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Abstract—Risk response planning is of importance for software project risk management (SPRM). In CMMI, risk management was in the third capability maturity level, which provides a framework for software project risk identification, assessment, risk planning, risk control. However, the CMMI-based SPRM currently lacks quantitative supporting tools, especially during the process of implementing software project risk planning. In this paper, an economic optimization model for selecting risk reduction actions in the phase of software project risk response planning is presented. Furthermore, an example taken from a Chinese software industry is illustrated to verify the application of this method. The research provides a risk decision method for project risk managers that can be used in the implementation of CMMI-based SPRM.

Keywords—Software project, risk management, CMMI, risk response planning.

I. INTRODUCTION

SOFTWARE project risk management is a relatively new research area in software engineering. It first came to the forefront with Boehm's tutorial on risk management [1]. This subject has made great progress in theories, methods as well as techniques and tools for about thirty years' development. Nowadays, the development of software process improvement (SPI) for software engineering practice has achieved greatly, which benefits software project risk management a lot. The combination of risk management and process management has also been a hotspot on the research of software project risk management. CMMI is one of the models of SPI and becomes more popular recently. In CMMI, risk management processes are a requirement for the Integrated Software Management key process area (KPA) at the third capability maturity level [2]. And risk management is merged into the same framework with process management. Thus, the CMMI-based SPRM can utilize more useful information of software organizations and make the software development in the direction of regularity and prediction. But at present, the risk management methods in the CMMI-based SPRM are still incomplete. A deep discussion will be made in the future. During the implementation of CMMI-based SPRM, this paper proposes an economic

optimization model that describes a risk abatement actions selection problem in the phase of risk response planning and an example of this model is illustrated. The model provides a risk decision-making method for software project management people.

II. CMMI-BASED SOFTWARE PROJECT RISK MANAGEMENT

Risk can be defined as the exposure to the probability that an event with adverse consequences might occur. All projects involve some amount of risk, resulting from them being temporary endeavors aimed at achieving some unique set of predetermined time, cost and performance objectives [3]. In software development projects, various risks are a key problem affecting performance, which may have undesirable consequences due to the uncertainties of the requirements, technologies, personnel, process, and organization.

CMMI provides guidance for improving software organization's processes and ability to manage the development, acquisition, and maintenance of products and services. In CMMI, risk management was in the third capability maturity level, which provides a framework for software project risk identification, assessment, risk planning, risk control.

The risk management process in the project execution was defined based on the CMMI model and has eight activities (Fig. 1) [4].

Fig. 1 Risk Management Process, based on the CMMI model

In Fig. 1, risk response planning is an important phase of implementing risk management. It is the process of developing

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options, and determining actions to enhance opportunities and reduce threats to the project's objectives. Then, selecting the best risk response from several options is often required [5].

In CMMI-base SPRM, risk repository and process database have played a crucial role. Risks of a project can be drawn from taxonomy-based risk checklist and other information about risk management can be found in the risk repository. Therefore, the process database is becoming a foundation for quantitatively managing software risk. In addition, the experiences of software project managers and experts can also help the execution of project risk management. Thus, CMMI-base SPRM can utilize more useful information of software organizations and relative persons, which will integrate the quantitative and qualitative methods of risk management.

This paper describes a risk abatement actions selection problem in implementing software project risk response development. Then, we focus on an economic optimization model for selecting risk reduction actions, so as to provide an efficient support for managers to make a risk decision.

III. OPTIMIZATION MODEL FORMULATION

A. The Risk Abatement Actions Selection Problem

In CMMI-based SPRM, the project risk response is based on the project planning. By several negotiations with project customers, software organization has understood customers' requirements gradually. Generally, the project work breakdown structure (WBS) according to software requirement specifications has been made and risk analysis for the software project has finished.

The WBS is a deliverable-oriented grouping of project elements that organizes and defines the total scope of the project. Elements at the lowest level of the WBS are called work packages, while elements at intermediate levels are called WBS branches. We will refer to each work package or WBS branch as a work element. The WBS serves as the basis for the analysis of risk actions. Some risk reduction actions may affect a single specific work package, while others may affect multiple work packages, a branch of the WBS, or even the entire project.

We assume that a risk event either happens or does not happen. By risk analysis, the risk events that will have serious adverse consequences should be taken more attention. Based on the project WBS, managers give the risk events from every work element and their probability. And managers also give the probable impact while these risk events occur. Here, the entries contain the impact caused by the events, if it occurs, to the work element, stated in monetary terms.

Based on the historical records from risk repository and experiences of experts, project managers propose lots of risk reduction actions to reduce threats to the project's objectives. Then, the experts will evaluate the cost of implementing these actions. The risk reduction actions may reduce the risk probability and/or risk impact. But on the whole, it will make sense only if implementing these risk reduction actions can truly reduce the total cost of this project. This is a risk abatement actions selection problem. One needs to address the

selection of the best combination of risk reduction actions for a given project scope and a given set of predicted risk events.

B. The Economic Optimization Model

Assuming that the work elements of the software project are all the components of the WBS. We define $s = 1, 2, \dots, S$ as the set S of work elements and $r = 1, 2, \dots, R$ as the set R of risk events. The probability of occurrence of a risk event r depends on its source s . We define a probability matrix $P = (p_{r,s})_{R \times S}$, where its element $p_{r,s}$ is the probability that source s will cause a risk event r . The occurrence of a risk event may impact one or more work elements of the software project. We define an impact matrix $M = (m_{r,w})_{R \times W}$, where its element $m_{r,w}$ is a monetary loss to work element w caused by risk event r . Our model allows us to include positive risk events, sometimes referred to as 'opportunities', which are events that can cause savings or additional profit. In such case, the entry will be negative. We define the expected impact matrix as the matrix G , where G is the product of the transposed probability matrix and the impact matrix. Then, each cell in the matrix G contains the sum of the impacts caused by the row work element, weighted by the probability of occurrence of the corresponding risk events. The sum of all the elements of the matrix G yields the total risk exposure of the project.

The matrix G can be expressed as (1) and the total expected risk loss (ERL) be expressed as (2):

$$G = P^T \times M = (g_{s,w})_{S \times W} = \left(\sum_{r=1}^R (p_{s,r} \times m_{r,w}) \right)_{S \times W} \quad (1)$$

$$ERL = \sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{w=1}^W (g_{s,w}) = \sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{w=1}^W \left(\sum_{r=1}^R p_{s,r} \times m_{r,w} \right) \quad (2)$$

By risk analysis, software project managers give the risk abatement actions and the cost of implementing them. We define $a = 1, 2, \dots, A$ as the set A of risk abatement actions and c_a as the abatement action cost, where the cost vector of risk abatement actions $C = (c_1, c_2, \dots, c_A)$.

Let $X_{a \times a}$ be a diagonal matrix with $X_{a \times a} = 1$ if action a is chosen and 0 otherwise. The matrix $X_{a \times a}$ is called action selection matrix. Let e_a be a column identity vector, where action a 1 and 0 otherwise. The abatement actions costs (AAC) can be expressed while a set of risk abatement actions were taken as follows:

$$AAC(X) = C \cdot X_{i,j} \cdot e_i = \sum_{i=1}^A c_i \cdot x_{i,i} \quad (3)$$

Risk abatement actions modify the probability and/or the impact of risk events. We define $v_{r,s,a}$ as the effect factor of action a on the probability of risk r originated from risk source s , where $V_{r,s} = (v_{r,s,1}, v_{r,s,2}, \dots, v_{r,s,A})$ and $u_{r,w,a}$ as

project risks?) can be treated with mathematical optimization tools and techniques, which provides an efficient support for managers to make risk decisions.

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